

29 **ABSTRACT**

30
31 Group synchrony occurs spontaneously during social interactions and is associated with
32 positive socio-affective outcomes, including reduced pain perception. While prior research
33 highlights the role of social bonding, the influence of pain and its emotional components (i.e.,
34 fear) on group synchrony remains unclear. Two experiments investigated (i) the impact of
35 synchrony on pain and (ii) the impact of pain on synchrony, social bonding, and affective
36 states. In both studies, synchrony enhanced social connectedness but did not consistently
37 reduce pain, and pain did not disrupt synchrony despite altering affective states. Experiment
38 1 showed that the threat of pain increased social bonding and arousal, suggesting that the
39 emotional component of pain functions as a social glue. Experiment 2 demonstrated that fear
40 of pain affected heart rates, mirroring patterns in chronic pain populations. Importantly, in both
41 studies, the sense of "worthwhileness" emerged as a critical factor influencing individual
42 contribution to synchronization and pain perception. Altogether, these results suggest that
43 group synchrony is resilient to pain, paving the way for therapeutic interventions harnessing
44 the benefits of collective motion.

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46 **Keywords:** Synchrony, pain, fear, social belongingness, worthwhileness

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BACKGROUND

Synchrony as social glue

Synchrony is a widespread phenomenon in which multiple agents or parts of living systems align their behavior in time [1,2]. In human-human interactions, synchrony is easily induced by rhythmical activities such as music or dance [3], but it can also emerge spontaneously in the absence of explicit rhythmic cues [4,5]. Interest in synchrony has grown, due to its positive effects on a wide range of socio-affective variables [6-8]. While joint rhythmic activities, such as those in religious rituals, have long been recognized for their role in strengthening social bounds [9], recent research has demonstrated that synchrony fosters affiliative tendencies [10], enhances positive emotions [11], and promotes prosocial behaviors such as altruism and trust [12, 13]. Importantly, the link between synchrony and socio-affective outcomes extends beyond motor coordination to physiological (i.e., cardiac synchrony, [14,15]) and neural levels (i.e., brain synchrony [16-18]). Consequently, synchrony is increasingly regarded as a hallmark of high-quality social interactions [19-21] however, the mechanisms linking synchrony to its socio-affective consequences remain debated [6-8].

On the one hand, synchronized movement could reduce perceptual uncertainty [22,23], facilitating the detection of self- and other-related information, and thereby fostering positive affect, affiliative tendencies as well as prosocial behaviors [24]. On the other hand, synchronized movement can elicit experiences of “self-other overlap”, integrating others within the self and extending self-bias processing to them [25,26] which, in turn, can increase affiliation and prosocial tendencies [27]. Alternatively, enjoying shared agency during synchronized movement may also be a key factor [28], amplifying positive affect [29-31]. Finally, a sense of joint commitment (e.g., working toward a common goal) may strengthen mutual trust, leading to prosocial outcomes [32-34]. However, these hypotheses are difficult to disentangle. For instance, when the shared activity is pleasant [e.g., 3, 28], the distinct contribution of synchrony, positive affect, shared agency and joint commitment are unclear. Moreover, these pathways are not mutually exclusive (e.g., perceptual uncertainty reduction could co-occur with self-other overlap experiences). Thus, while the precise mechanisms underlying synchrony’s socio-affective benefits remain unclear, they likely involve both affective components and self-other information overlap.

Synchrony and pain, a novel intersection of social and affective processes

103 Moving together in synchrony has a compelling effect: the reduction of pain
104 perception [3, 18, 35 - 41]. Pain, one of the most evolutionary ancient neural processes, is
105 traditionally understood as an unpleasant sensation resulting from tissue lesions [42]. Yet, just
106 as synchrony, pain is deeply intertwined with social and affective mechanisms.

107

108 First, regarding its association with social mechanisms, physical pain and social pain
109 (i.e., social rejection) activate overlapping brain regions [43,44]. Conversely, affective
110 attachment is linked with the release of oxytocin and opioids, two neurotransmitters also
111 involved in pain reduction [45-47]. Supporting this link, the sociometer hypothesis [48]
112 postulates that self-esteem reflects social integration, and several studies have already
113 established an association between self-esteem, social integration and both physical and
114 social pain [49,50]. Synchrony has been suggested to modulate pain through social bonding
115 [3,35,41], though the role of self-esteem and meaningful contributions, distinct yet overlapping
116 with social belonging, remains unexplored [51].

117

118 Second, pain encompasses a strong emotional component [52], with an overlapping
119 of its neural basis with emotional responses, self-awareness and time perception [53]. As a
120 negative affective state, pain triggers behavioral and physiological stress responses [54,55]
121 and can lead to '*fear of pain*', resulting in kinesiophobia (i.e., fear of movement) or placebo
122 effects, even in the absence of noxious stimulation [56]. Moreover, pain sensitivity is
123 influenced by emotions, with negative emotions amplifying pain and positive emotions
124 attenuating it, a phenomenon known as "affective analgesia". Since synchrony enhances
125 positive emotions [29-31], it may reduce pain perception by promoting positive affect.
126 However, prior studies often involve inherently pleasurable activities such as playing music
127 [38] or dancing together [3,41], making it difficult to delineate the effects of synchrony from
128 those of the enjoyable rhythmic activity itself.

129

130 Overall, synchrony and pain are not only interconnected but are also both deeply
131 embedded within social and affective processes. However, the mechanisms behind this
132 relationship remain unclear. Current research has primarily examined how synchrony reduces
133 pain, yet how pain, in turn, affects synchrony is largely unknown. This unilateral approach
134 leaves a critical gap in our understanding of their interaction.

135

136 *Synchrony Under Pain and Fear: Social, Emotional, and Motor Influences*

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138 Since pain and socio-affective processing share common mechanisms [43-47], and
139 socio-affective states influence synchrony [57], one might expect pain to disrupt synchrony by

140 weakening interpersonal bonds and/or inducing social rejection. Alternatively, given that
141 negative emotions reduce synchrony [58,59], the negative valence of pain, or even the mere
142 fear of pain, could disrupt synchrony. Finally, pain may affect synchrony by altering timing
143 behaviors [52], that could be reflected in movement kinematics, such as frequency and
144 amplitude, both key constituents of group synchronization [60]. While all these hypotheses
145 predict a reduction of synchrony due to pain, each proposes a distinct explanatory pathway.
146 To our knowledge, no study has directly examined the impact of pain or its fear on synchrony,
147 nor the potential role of social, emotional, and kinematic mechanisms in this relationship.
148 Furthermore, if synchrony decreases pain while pain, conversely, disrupts synchrony, which
149 of these effects predominates?

150

151 To answer this question, we conducted two studies. Specifically, we aimed to (i)
152 assess the effects of synchrony on pain perception, social bonding, and emotional states
153 [4,32], and (ii) evaluate the impact of pain and its fear on synchronization and its kinematic
154 constituents [60], as well as on social bonding and emotional states [49,50,54,55]. As a proxy
155 for studying pain and its emotional component, we administered aversive electrodermal
156 stimulation following a validated fear-conditioning protocol with unpredictable aversive events
157 [61-63].

158

159 In the first experiment, groups of five participants (quintets) were instructed to achieve
160 group synchrony while one participant received aversive electrodermal stimulation. This
161 design allowed us to examine how the stimulation influenced synchrony at the group level, its
162 socio-affective consequences and its effects on movement kinematics.

163

164 The second experiment partially replicated this protocol with groups of four
165 participants (quartets) to address limitations from the quintet experiment (see section
166 Discussion), and to explore the role of spontaneous and instructed synchronization conditions.
167 In this experiment, two participants received stimulation, allowing sample comparisons
168 between participants.

169

170 In both experiments, motion recordings were collected to assess collective
171 synchrony, individual contributions to group synchrony, and the extent to which aversive
172 stimulation affected key kinematics constituents of synchrony (i.e., frequency and amplitude).
173 Additionally, participants' heart rates were monitored as an implicit physiological measure of
174 affective response to aversive stimulation [52-54]. Finally, participants completed self-reports
175 of affective states [64], pain perception [65] and social bonding [51,66].

176

177 **EXPERIMENT 1 (Quintets)**

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179 **METHOD**

180

181 *Participants*

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183 Thirty participants (11 women, mean age = 21.96 ± 2.74) were recruited from the
184 student population at the University of Montpellier and assigned to six mixed-gender quintets.

185

186 *Experimental procedure*

187

188 Participants were positioned in a complete graph configuration consisting of five
189 individual nodes [67]. They were instructed to perform oscillatory movements with their right
190 forearm under four blocked experimental conditions: (i) **NO -VISION**: Participants performed
191 the movement at their preferred frequency without visual access to one another. This condition
192 allowed us to determine their individual “natural” frequency (i.e., eigenfrequency) and to
193 establish a threshold for “spurious” synchrony within each group; (ii) **VISION**: Participants
194 maintained visual contact and synchronized their movements. This condition served as a
195 baseline for coupled group synchronization; (iii) **STIMULATION**: Participants synchronized
196 their movement while maintaining visual contact, with one participant receiving intermittent,
197 irregular, and unpleasant stimulation during half of the trials in the block. This condition allowed
198 us to compute coupled group synchronization when one member experienced painful
199 stimulation; (iv) **UNCERTAINTY**: Participants synchronized their movements while facing the
200 uncertainty of receiving aversive stimulation. This condition allowed us to assess the effect of
201 fear — without actual stimulation — on synchronization. The conditions were presented in a
202 fixed order across all groups, with each condition consisting of six trials of 45 seconds each
203 (see **Figure 1** for a graphical representation).

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207 **Figure 1:** Graphical illustration of the group network and the experimental conditions (top);
 208 markers and electrodes placement on participants' effector (bottom).

209

210 *Pain induction procedure*

211

212 Electrodermal stimulations were delivered via two surface Ag/AgCl electrodes (e.g.,
 213 Sensor Medics; 0.8-1.0 cm diameter) filled with electroconductive gel (e.g., K-Y gel) and
 214 placed on the participant's forearm (see **Figure 1** for graphical illustration). The electrodes
 215 were connected to a Digitimer stimulator, which delivered the aversive electrodermal
 216 stimulation. Pain induction followed the NPU-threat test protocol [61-63], which calibrates the
 217 stimulation intensity to individual pain sensitivity. Participants rated a series of shocks on a
 218 visual analog scale from 0 to 10 (0 = no sensation to 10 = extremely unpleasant/painful). Four
 219 sample shocks were delivered while participants performed oscillatory movements with their

220 right arm, starting at 5 mA and increasing incrementally until a rating of “7” (moderately
221 unpleasant) was reached¹. To maintain a double-blind procedure, neither participants nor the
222 experimenter were aware of which participant would receive the stimulation. A research
223 assistant responsible for pain threshold calibration monitored the stimulation throughout the
224 experiment.

225

226 *Self-reports*

227

228 Before and after each experimental block, participants reported their affective states
229 using the *Self-Assessment Manikin scale* (SAM, [64]), a validated pictorial measure of
230 emotional arousal and valence previously used in synchrony studies [31, 58]. They also
231 evaluated their experience of self-other overlap using the Inclusion of the *Other in the Self*
232 *scale* (IOS, [66]), a pictorial measure of social connectedness commonly used in research on
233 synchrony and social bonding [3,13]. After the **STIMULATION** and **UNCERTAINTY**
234 conditions, participants reported their subjective experience of pain (i.e., intensity and
235 localization) using adapted items from the *Vicarious Pain Questionnaire* (VPQ [65]), providing
236 a measure of pain perception and potential nocebo effects - see **Supplementary Material**. At
237 the end of the experiment, participants rated their perceived individual contribution to the
238 collective task as a proxy for self-esteem, based on items adapted from the *William’s ostracism*
239 *scale* [51]².

240

241 *Motion recordings*

242

243 Participants' movements were recorded using an infra-red camera system (Vicon
244 System, Nexus) at a sampling rate of 100Hz. A set of three markers was placed on the
245 shoulder, elbow and index finger of each participant’s right arm (see **Figure 1** for illustration).

246

247 *Electrocardiogram recordings*

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249 The participants' physiological state was monitored using electrocardiogram (ECG)
250 recordings. Two electrodes were placed on the right and left sides of the chest, with a

¹ If the threshold of « 7 » (moderately unpleasant) was reached before the fourth shock, additional shocks of the same intensity were administered. conversely, if the rating of « 4 » was not reached after four shocks, the maximum tested intensity was used.

² Before the experiment, participants also completed a series of traits questionnaires measuring affective, cognitive, motor and vicarious empathy, as well as autistic traits, dark-personality traits, anxiety, and emotion dysregulation. These questionnaires served as a filler task during the experimental setup. They are not reported in the present manuscript.

251 reference electrode positioned on the hip. ECG signals were recorded using two different ECG
252 systems, at sampling rates of 2,148 Hz and 519 Hz respectively.

253

254 *Motion pre-processing*

255

256 Motion data were pre-processed using the Python package “SciPy” [68]. A two-pass
257 fourth-order Butterworth low-pass filter (cut-off frequency: 10 Hz) was applied to reduce jitter
258 and artifacts. Principal component analysis (PCA) was then used to reduce the 3D time series
259 of finger positions into a one-dimensional time series. Next, the amplitude and phase of
260 participants’ motion were extracted using the Hilbert transform, and a peak-to-peak detection
261 algorithm was used to compute movement cycle durations, which were converted into
262 frequency (Hz).

263

264 Group synchronization was quantified using the Kuramoto model [69], which
265 measures the phase dispersion of coupled oscillators. The model’s output — the order
266 parameter — provides an index of synchronization ranging from 0 (no synchronization) to 1
267 (perfect synchronization), capturing the temporal evolution of group synchrony [31, 58, 67].
268 Individual synchronization scores were also computed by determining each participant’s
269 relative phase with respect to the group’s overall phase, providing a measure of how much
270 each participant contributed to the group performance.

271

272 In addition, exploratory analyses were conducted on velocity profiles considering that
273 previous research suggested that pain and fear of pain influence movement dynamics [70,71].
274 These analyses are reported in the **Supplementary Material**.

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276 *ECG pre-processing*

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278 ECG data were pre-processed using the “NeuroKit” package [72]. A two-pass fifth-
279 order Butterworth high-pass filter (cut-off frequency: 0.5 Hz) was applied to remove artifacts
280 and power line noise. R-peaks were detected as local maxima in the QRS complexes and
281 converted into heart rate (i.e., beats per minute, BPM).

282

283 *Statistical analyses*

284

285 Mixed models were used to assess the effects of experimental conditions (**NO-**
286 **VISION, VISION, STIMULATION** and **UNCERTAINTY**) on synchronization scores (group and
287 individual), physiological state (heart-rate), kinematic parameters (amplitude and frequency),

288 and affective and affiliative states (self-reports). Experimental conditions were modeled as
289 fixed predictors, while groups and participants were modeled as random effects. Holm-
290 Bonferroni corrections were applied for multiple comparisons. Additionally, non-parametric t-
291 tests were conducted to contrast trials with and without stimulation within the **STIMULATION**
292 condition, assessing their impact on synchronization scores, physiological states, and
293 kinematics. Similar comparisons were made for pain perception across baseline,
294 **STIMULATION** and **UNCERTAINTY** conditions, contrasting participants who received
295 stimulation with those who did not. Finally, Spearman correlations were computed to examine
296 associations between individual synchronization scores, heart rate, pain perception, affective
297 states, and social bonding (IOS scores) obtained in the **STIMULATION** condition, as well as
298 their relationship with self-reported ostracism.

299

300 **RESULTS**

301

302 *Synchrony and its kinematics constituents*

303

304 Group synchrony was influenced by the experimental conditions ($F(3,135) = 829.76$,
305 $p < .001$ and $R^2 = .95$), with lower scores in the **NO-VISION** condition compared to all other
306 conditions (adjusted $ps < .001$). However, there was no significant difference in group
307 synchrony between trials with and without stimulation ($W(34) = 172$, $p = .767$). A similar
308 pattern was observed for individual contribution to group synchrony, with lower scores in the
309 **NO-VISION** condition ($F(3, 711) = 1368.68$, $p < .001$ and $R^2 = .85$) but no difference between
310 trials within the **STIMULATION** condition ($W(172) = 2653$, $p = .829$). Overall, synchrony
311 scores were affected by visual coupling but not by the administration of unpleasant stimulation
312 - see **Figure 2** for graphical representation and **Table 1** in Supplementary Material for a
313 summary of descriptive statistics.

314

315 Participants' movement frequency was influenced by experimental conditions ($F(3,$
316 $710) = 587.55$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = .80$), showing a steady increase from the **NO-VISION** to the
317 **UNCERTAINTY** condition (adjusted $ps < .010$). Changes in frequency were accompanied by
318 a decreased in mean amplitude ($F(3, 711) = 5.99$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = .31$), with a significant
319 reduction in the **UNCERTAINTY** condition compared to the **NO-VISION** (adjusted $p = .007$)
320 and **VISION** conditions (adjusted $p = .016$). However, there were no changes in movement
321 frequency ($W(178) = 4084$, $p = .924$) and amplitude ($W(178) = 4080$, $p = .924$) between trials
322 with and without stimulation within the **STIMULATION** condition. Overall, both movement
323 frequency and amplitude — key components of group synchrony — were modulated by visual

324 coupling but not by the administration of unpleasant stimulation - see **Figure 2** for graphical
 325 representation and **Table 1** in Supplementary Material for a summary of descriptive statistics.
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328

329 **Figure 2:** Graphical illustration of a sample finger movement time series, phase and group
 330 synchrony measured via the Kuramoto order parameter (top). Summary statistics of individual
 331 contributions to synchronization (left), movement frequency (middle), and movement
 332 amplitude (right) across experimental conditions.

333

334 *Pain perception and socio-affective states*

335

336 Participants who received the stimulation reported higher unpleasantness ratings
 337 than those who did not ($W(28) = 14.5, p = .001$). Importantly, these ratings tended to deviate
 338 from the targeted “moderately unpleasant” level set during the threshold procedure ($W(5) =$

339 0, $p = .054$). Interestingly, some participants who did not receive the stimulation also reported
 340 experiencing unpleasant sensations, with a trend toward deviation from the expected “0 - no
 341 sensation” rating ($W(23) = 15$, $p = .048$). However, these participants described their
 342 sensations as more diffuse and generalized compared to those receiving stimulation (Fisher
 343 Test, $p = .001$). Overall, while participants who received the stimulation confirmed
 344 experiencing localized unpleasant sensations, their reported unpleasantness was lower than
 345 during the thresholding phase.

346

347 IOS scores were influenced by the experimental conditions ($F(3,110) = 13.15$, $p <$
 348 $.001$ and $R^2 = .38$), with lower IOS scores in the **NO-VISION** condition compared to all other
 349 conditions (*adjusted ps* $< .001$). In contrast, there was no significant difference between
 350 conditions for emotional valence ($F(3, 111) = 0.08$, $p = .971$ and $R^2 = .10$) and arousal ($F(3,$
 351 $111) = 0.56$ $p = .643$ and $R^2 = .01$). Thus, experimental manipulation affected experienced
 352 social connectedness but not emotional states - see **Figure 3** for graphical representation and
 353 **Table 2** in Supplementary Material for a descriptive statistical summary.

354

355 Participants’ heart rates were influenced by experimental conditions ($F(1, 616) =$
 356 22.19 , $p < .001$ and $R^2 = .18$), with a significant increase in heart rate in the **STIMULATION**
 357 and **UNCERTAINTY** conditions compared to the **NO-VISION** (*adjusted p* $= .010$ and $p = .001$)
 358 and **VISION** conditions (*adjusted p* $= .056$ and $p = .010$). However, there was no significant
 359 difference in heart rate between trials with and without stimulation ($W(154) = 2889$, $p = .589$).
 360 Overall, participants’ heart rates increased when there was a threat of unpleasant stimulation,
 361 even in the absence of actual stimulation - see **Figure 3** for graphical representation and **Table**
 362 **1** in Supplementary Material for a descriptive statistical summary.

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364

365 **Figure 3:** Graphical representation of pain intensity (left) as a function of stimulation induction,
 366 along with IOS scores (middle) and heart rates (right) across experimental conditions.

367

368 *Zero-order correlations*

369

370 Spearman correlations revealed a negative association between feelings of ostracism
371 and individual contributions to group synchrony ($r = -.54, p < .001$). Feelings of ostracism
372 displayed a trend toward a positive association with pain sensation ($r = .36, p = .080$). In
373 contrast, emotional arousal was positively associated both with pain intensity ($r = .57, p = .019$)
374 and IOS scores ($r = .49, p = .038$), indicating a link between heightened emotional arousal,
375 increased pain perception, and stronger social bonding experiences. Overall, feelings of
376 ostracism were linked to increased pain sensations and decreased individual contributions to
377 group synchrony, whereas emotional arousal heightened both pain perception and
378 experiences of social bonding.

379

380 **DISCUSSION**

381

382 The quintet experiment confirmed that a visually coupled group can easily achieve
383 movement synchronization [1 - 5]. It also replicated previously observed associations of
384 interpersonal synchrony with social bonding [6 - 8] and with decreased pain perception [3, 18,
385 35 - 41]. However, despite clear subjective reports of pain sensations and objective increases
386 in heart rates, the unpleasant electrodermal stimulation did not disrupt synchrony.
387 Nevertheless, individual contribution to group synchrony tended to decrease with feelings of
388 ostracism, which in turn, showed a trend toward increased pain intensity ratings. Interestingly,
389 emotional arousal was positively associated with both pain intensity and social bonding.
390 Altogether, these results support the hypothesis that synchrony may influence pain perception
391 through social bonding [3,35,41], yet further investigations are required.

392

393 The interpretation of the above results face limitations. First, although the stimulation
394 elicited physiological responses (i.e., increased heart rate), it did not lead to detectable
395 changes in subjective affective states. However, reports of emotional arousal were associated
396 with both heightened pain sensations and an unexpected increase in social bonding. This
397 suggests that the pain stimulation may not have been strong enough to disrupt synchrony.
398 Instead, post-experiment debriefings indicated that participants may have experienced a “thrill
399 of fear” rather than genuine fear in response to the threat of stimulation [73, 74]. Additionally,
400 in each group, only one out of five partners received the stimulation, preventing statistical
401 comparisons between stimulated and non-stimulated individuals within the same session.
402 Additionally, the lack of change in the valence of affective states suggests that perturbation,
403 being restricted to a single individual per group, may not have been strong enough to

404 destabilize the network of synchronized partners. Finally, the ease of achieving group
405 synchrony could also explain its stability. Given that synchrony is a robust socially embodied
406 pattern of coordination, it may be difficult to disrupt with a relatively mild perturbation.

407

408 To address these limitations, the quartet experiment was designed to i) increase
409 stimulation impact delivering a series of shocks instead of single pulses, ii) enhance statistical
410 comparisons by reducing group size ($n = 4$) and stimulating half of the participants (two out of
411 four), and iii) increase task difficulty by reducing visual coupling between participants. To
412 achieve the latter, a cylinder was placed at the center of the network, restricting participants
413 to peripheral vision for synchronization. Additionally, synchronization instructions were
414 manipulated to investigate the impact of the stimulation on individual, spontaneous and goal-
415 oriented synchronization. These modifications aimed to increase task complexity, stimulation
416 intensity, and to delineate the role of joint commitment, to provide clearer insights into the
417 interaction between pain, synchrony, and social bonding.

418

419 **EXPERIMENT 2 (QUARTET)**

420

421 **METHOD**

422

423 *Participants*

424

425 For the quartet experiment, 40 participants (19 women, mean age = 26.83 ± 6.83)
426 were recruited and assigned to 10 mixed-gender quartets.

427

428 *Experimental procedure*

429

430 Participants were positioned in a square formation, with a cylinder placed at the
431 center to obstruct their view of the person directly in front of them, thereby increasing the
432 difficulty of the group synchronization task. Participants performed oscillatory movements with
433 their right forearm under three experimental conditions: (i) **SOLO**: Participants performed the
434 movement at their preferred pace without seeing each other, allowing to gauge their
435 spontaneous movement frequency (eigenfrequency) and establish a “spurious” synchrony
436 threshold; (ii) **TOGETHER**: Participants followed the same instruction as in the **SOLO**
437 condition but were visually coupled with their left and right partners; (iii) **SYNCHRO**:
438 Participants were explicitly instructed to achieve group synchrony. The **SOLO** condition was
439 completed first, followed either by the **TOGETHER** or **SYNCHRO** condition. A second **SOLO**
440 condition was implemented before participants performed the remaining condition (i.e., either

441 **TOGETHER** or **SYNCHRO**). Each condition consisted of six trials lasting one minute each,
442 starting with two baseline trials (no stimulation), followed by four trials in which unpleasant
443 stimulation was delivered. The stimulation consisted of a series of aversive electrodermal
444 shocks, administered randomly during the trial. Participants underwent the same double-blind
445 pain induction procedure as in the quintet experiment, following the NPU-threat test [61-63],
446 with pain intensity calibrated to ratings of “7” (moderately unpleasant). Stimulated participants
447 (**STIMULATION** group) experienced two trials with stimulation for each condition, resulting in
448 a total of two **BASELINE** trials (no stimulation), two **PAIN** trials (with stimulation), and two
449 **FEAR** trials (threat of stimulation but no actual shocks); See **Figure 4** for a graphical illustration
450 of the experimental design.

451

452 *Self-reports*

453

454 In addition to SAM, IOS and pain sensations measures collected in the quintet
455 experiment, participants also reported their fear of pain (intensity ratings) after each condition
456 - see **Supplementary Material**.

457

458

459 **Figure 4:** Graphical illustration of the experimental conditions in the quartet experiment.
460 Markers and electrodes placement were identical to that in the quintet experiment.

461

462 *Statistical analyses*

463

464 Mixed models contrasted trial types (i.e., **BASELINE**, **FEAR**, **PAIN**) and social
465 context (i.e., **SOLO**, **TOGETHER**, **SYNCHRO**) as predictors of cardiac activity (HR), and
466 individual kinematics (synchrony scores, movement frequency and amplitude). For group
467 synchrony, mixed models contrasted only **BASELINE** and **PAIN** trials, along with social
468 context, since **FEAR** and **PAIN** trials were manipulated between participants and occurred
469 simultaneously at the group level (i.e., one individual receiving stimulation induced fear in
470 another within the same trial). For self-reports, mixed models contrasted participant groups
471 (**NO STIMULATION** vs. **STIMULATION**) and social context as predictors of pain-related
472 experiences (intensity and fear of pain), emotional states (valence and arousal) and social
473 closeness (IOS scores). Experimental conditions, trial types and participant groups were
474 included as fixed predictors, while groups and participants were treated as random effect.
475 Holm-Bonferroni corrections were applied to adjust for multiple comparisons. Additionally,
476 Spearman correlations were conducted to assess associations between individual
477 synchronization scores, heart rates, pain perception, affective states and social bonding (IOS)
478 obtained in the **SYNCHRO** condition with self-reports of ostracism.

479

480

481 **RESULTS**

482

483 *Synchrony and its kinematic contributors*

484

485 Group synchrony scores were influenced by the experimental conditions ($F(2, 225)$
486 $= 1273.91, p < .001, R^2 = .92$), with an increase in group synchrony from **SOLO** to **SYNCHRO**
487 conditions (*adjusted ps* $< .001$). However, there was no effect or interaction with pain (*ps* $>$
488 $.050$). A similar pattern as observed for individual contributions to group synchrony, which also
489 increased from **SOLO** to **SYNCHRO** conditions ($F(2, 945) = 696.81, p < .001, R^2 = .60,$
490 *adjusted ps* $< .001$), again with no effect or interaction with pain (*ps* $> .050$).

491

492 Movement frequency was influenced by experimental conditions ($F(2, 942) = 26.45,$
493 $p < .001, R^2 = .46$), with an increase in frequency in the **SYNCHRO** condition compared to the
494 others conditions (*adjusted p* $< .001$). This increase in frequency was accompanied by a
495 decrease in movement amplitude ($F(2, 942) = 9.79, p < .001, R^2 = .22$), with a lower amplitude
496 in the **SYNCHRO** condition compared to others conditions (*adjusted p* $< .010$). Overall,
497 synchrony scores, movement frequency and amplitude were affected by social context (i.e.,
498 visual coupling and instructions to synchronize), but not by the fear or exposure to unpleasant
499 stimulation - see **Figure 5** for graphical representation and **Table 5** in Supplementary Material
500 for a summary of descriptive statistics.

501

502

503 **Figure 5:** Graphical illustration of a sample of group synchrony time series (top) along with
 504 summary statistics of individual synchrony scores (left), as well as movement frequency
 505 (middle) and amplitude (right) across experimental conditions and trials types.

506

507 *Pain sensations and socio-affective states*

508

509 Unpleasantness ratings were influenced by the administration of stimulation ($F(1,$
 510 $145) = 248.87, p < .001, R^2 = .66$), with stimulated participants reporting stronger unpleasant
 511 sensations compared to those who did not receive stimulation (*adjusted ps* $< .001$).
 512 Interestingly, unpleasant ratings among stimulated participants deviated from the target level
 513 of “moderately unpleasant”, set during the threshold calibration ($W(78) = 0, p < .001$). As
 514 observed in the quintet experiment, some of the non-stimulated participants also reported

515 unpleasant sensations ($W(78) = 153, p < .001$). However, their sensations were described as
516 more diffuse and general, whereas stimulated participants reported localized pain (Fisher
517 Test, $p = .001$). Fear of pain was also influenced by the stimulation ($F(1, 145) = 16.54, p <$
518 $.001, R^2 = .29$), with stimulated participants reporting more intense fear of pain compared to
519 non-stimulated participants ($ps < .001$). However, social context did not influence pain intensity
520 or fear of pain - see **Figure 6** for graphical representations.

521

522 Social bonding, as measured by IOS scores, was influenced by experimental
523 conditions ($F(2,130) = 9.28, p < .001$ and $R^2 = .14$), with a steady increase in perceived social
524 closeness from the **SOLO** to the **SYNCHRO** condition (*adjusted* $p < .001$). While there was
525 no difference between stimulated and non-stimulated participants for emotional arousal (F
526 $(1,130) = 1.44, p = .232$), emotional valence differed between them ($F(1,130) = 9.89, p = .002$
527 and $R^2 = .13$), with stimulated participants reporting a decrease in emotional valence (*adjusted*
528 $p < .001$). No interaction was found between stimulation and experimental conditions. Overall,
529 social closeness and emotional valence were distinctly influenced by experimental conditions
530 and stimulation - see **Figure 6** for graphical representation and **Table 6** in Supplementary
531 Material for a descriptive statistical summary.

532

533 Participants' heart rates were influenced by trial type ($F(2, 928) = 6.46, p = .002$ and
534 $R^2 = .21$), with higher heart rates observed in trials with fear of stimulation (*adjusted* $p = .005$)
535 compared to baseline trials. However, there was no effect of the social context on heart rate,
536 and no interaction with stimulation. Overall, fear of receiving stimulation increased heart rates,
537 but social context did not influence physiological responses - see **Figure 6** for graphical
538 representation and **Table 5** for in Supplementary Material for a descriptive statistical summary.

539

540

541

542

543 **Figure 6:** Graphical illustration of the intensity of pain and fear of pain (top left and right), IOS
 544 (bottom left) and valence scores (middle) and heart rate (right) across experimental conditions.

545

546 *Zero-order correlations*

547

548 Spearman correlations revealed a positive association between experiences of
 549 ostracism and pain intensity ($r = .52, p < .001$), indicating that higher ostracism was linked to
 550 stronger pain sensations. Ostracism was also negatively associated with IOS scores ($r = -.42,$
 551 $p = .008$) and emotional valence ($r = -.38, p = .017$), suggesting that greater ostracism was
 552 related to lower social connectedness and more negative emotional states.

553

554 In contrast, individual contributions to synchrony were positively associated with IOS
 555 scores ($r = .32, p = .041$), and IOS scores were positively correlated with emotional valence (r
 556 $= .49, p = .001$), indicating that greater social connectedness was linked to stronger individual
 557 synchronization and more positive emotional experiences. Finally, pain intensity showed a
 558 trend toward a negative correlation with emotional valence ($r = -.27, p = .099$), suggesting a

559 potential link between higher pain intensity and more negative emotional states. Overall,
560 ostracism was associated with greater pain intensity, lower social connectedness and more
561 negative emotions. Higher experiences of social connectedness were associated with
562 stronger synchrony and more positive emotional valence.

563

564 **DISCUSSION**

565

566 The quartet experiment partially replicated the results from the quintet experiment,
567 demonstrating that synchrony was influenced by social context (visual coupling and
568 instructions) and was positively associated with social bonding. Notably, the quartet
569 experiment revealed that visual coupling alone (i.e., without explicit instruction to synchronize),
570 was sufficient to enhance both synchrony and social bonding. This aligns with previous studies
571 showing that the mere perception of others is sufficient to induce interpersonal synchrony and
572 increase social connectedness [4,5, 67]. In contrast to the quintet experiment, pain sensations
573 were not influenced by the social context, and participants tended to report lower pain intensity
574 than in the baseline, not only in the **SYNCHRO** condition, but also in the **TOGETHER** and
575 **SOLO** conditions. This discrepancy between experiments requires further investigation to
576 delineate the role of synchrony from that of a shared collective goal.

577

578 Previous studies investigating the impact of synchrony on pain used different
579 synchronization tasks such as dance [4,41], drumming [38] or rowing [40], contrasting
580 synchronous, asynchronous, or pseudo-synchronous conditions. These experimental designs
581 may have introduced greater task difficulty or influenced the perceptual outcomes of the
582 collective performance, potentially affecting pain perception [4, 38, 40, 41]. In the quartet
583 experiment, no explicit shared goal was present in the **SOLO** and **TOGETHER** conditions,
584 suggesting that a collective goal may play a key role in pain modulation [28, 32 - 34]. This
585 hypothesis is supported by the correlations observed in both studies between experiences of
586 ostracism and pain intensity. Taken together, these results suggest that it may not be social
587 bonding *per se* that influences pain alleviation but rather the experience of “worthwhileness”
588 — the subjective feeling of making a meaningful contribution toward task achievement.

589

590 Consistent with the quintet experiment, the quartet experiment confirmed that pain
591 did not disrupt synchrony, despite its impact on individuals’ affective states. Importantly, the
592 quartet experiment revealed that fear of pain induced more pronounced physiological changes
593 than pain itself. Comparable findings have been reported in chronic pain and anxiety disorders,
594 where fear of pain elicits stronger avoidance behaviors and physiological responses than

595 actual pain [75 - 77]. The quartet experiment extends these findings by demonstrating that
596 such behavioral and physiological effects also manifest in group settings.

597

598 **GENERAL DISCUSSION**

599

600 This research aimed to clarify the association between group synchrony and pain.
601 Previous studies showed that synchrony reduces pain sensations through social bonding, yet
602 little attention has been given to the impact of pain and its emotional component on group
603 synchrony. To address this gap, two experiments were conducted to i) assess the effects of
604 synchrony on pain perception, social bonding, and emotional states, and ii) explore how pain
605 affects group synchrony. To our knowledge, this is the first study that directly examined the
606 impact of pain or its fear on synchrony, and the potential role of social, emotional, and
607 kinematic mechanisms in this relationship.

608

609 Both experiments confirmed that synchrony emerges naturally through sensorimotor
610 coupling [1 - 5], and in the quartet experiment, synchrony was observed even without explicit
611 synchronization instructions [4,5]. Additionally, both studies demonstrated that group
612 synchrony enhances social bonding by inducing experiences of self-other overlap [6 - 8].
613 Notably, in the quintet experiment, social bonding was positively correlated with pain ratings
614 and emotional arousal during the **STIMULATION** condition, suggesting that pain (or its
615 anticipation) may reinforce social connectedness. This finding aligns with prior research
616 showing that painful rituals, such as those involving piercing and cutting in religious
617 ceremonies, can be more effective than synchrony alone in fostering social bonding [78 - 81].
618 Thus, this positive association of social bonding with pain and emotional arousal observed
619 during stimulation in the quintet experiment suggests that pain — and the shared experience
620 of its anticipation — acts as a social glue, strengthening group identity [82] and cohesion [83].

621

622 *Impact of Pain on Affective States*

623

624 Both experiments demonstrated that social bonding increased with synchrony, yet
625 they diverge in their findings on how stimulation impacted affective states. In the quintet
626 experiment, pain stimulation did not alter subjective affective reports, despite its influence on
627 participants' cardiac activity. In contrast, the quartet experiment revealed an increase in
628 negative affective states in participants receiving the stimulation. This discrepancy may stem
629 from differences in stimulation protocols. In the quintet experiment, participants received
630 random electrodermal stimulations during half of the trials in the **STIMULATION** condition,
631 which may have elicited a “thrill of fear” rather than genuine fear [73, 74]. This interpretation

632 is supported by positive correlations between pain intensity, social bonding, and emotional
633 arousal. Conversely, in the quartet experiment, participants received multiple stimulations
634 during the whole experiment, leading to a sense of resignation toward an uncontrollable
635 situation. Post-experiment debriefings suggested experiences resembling “learned
636 helplessness” due to the loss of control and the inability to escape the stimulation [84,85].
637 Thus, the different pain administration methods may have induced qualitatively distinct
638 affective states and future studies should delineate the effect of emotional arousal and valence
639 on the effect of synchrony on pain threshold.

640

641 *Vicarious pain and the nocebo effect*

642

643 Interestingly, in both studies, some non-stimulated participants reported experiencing
644 unpleasant sensations, albeit described as general and diffuse compared to the localized pain
645 reported by those who actually received the stimulation. Although investigating the nocebo
646 effect was not the primary goal of this study, these findings align with previous research
647 showing that some individuals — referred to as vicarious responders — experience pain when
648 observing others in pain. Such individuals are also more susceptible to emotional contagion,
649 a trait linked to empathy [86]. Moreover, these vicarious responders tend to exhibit atypical
650 bodily self-awareness and susceptibility to body illusions [87, 88]. Future research should
651 further investigate how inter-individual differences in vicarious pain responses relate to
652 empathy-related traits, as well as plasticity of the sense of agency and body ownership [56].

653

654 *Resilience of synchrony and the role of fear*

655

656 In both studies, pain stimulation did not disrupt synchronization, suggesting that
657 group synchrony is resilient to this type of perturbation, despite its measurable effect on
658 individuals’ cardiac activity. Interestingly, the quartet experiment revealed that fear of pain
659 induced stronger physiological changes than pain itself [56,89,90]. Although beyond the
660 original scope of this study, complementary analyses of velocity profiles explored findings from
661 previous research suggesting that pain and fear of pain influence movement dynamics [70,71].
662 (see **Supplementary Material**). These analyses revealed changes in velocity profiles related
663 to pain and fear of pain, though substantial inter-individual variability was observed. Future
664 investigations should explore factors influencing these differences, such as participants’
665 natural movement frequency, a key variable in pain reduction through music [91]. Taken
666 together, these findings suggest that while pain’s physiological and kinematics effects are
667 measurable, they do not interact with social context variables such as group synchrony.

668

670

671 To the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to investigate the impact of pain on
672 group synchrony. A recent study [92] showed that an inflammation-induced sickness can
673 decrease spontaneous interpersonal synchrony, though that study involved dizziness rather
674 than pain. Given previous research demonstrating that pain acts as social glue [78 - 81], one
675 might expect pain to increase social bonding. However, in the quartet experiment, participants
676 who received stimulation reported lower IOS scores than non-stimulated participants. This
677 suggests that the effect of synchrony on social connectedness may be stronger for those
678 anticipating pain rather than actually experiencing it.

679

680 While prior studies emphasized social bonding as a key link between synchrony and
681 pain alleviation [3, 18, 35 - 41], the present findings suggest a more nuanced explanation:
682 rather than social bonding alone, it may be the feeling of being perceived by others as
683 "worthwhile" and in control of the situation (i.e., efficient in goal achievement) — whether
684 collective or individual —, that drives the association between synchrony and pain [84]. This
685 interpretation aligns with studies showing that social feedback reduces group synchrony [58].
686 The concept of "worthwhileness", derived from the sociometer hypothesis [48], may explain
687 these findings. Self-esteem, as a barometer of social integration has been linked to modulation
688 of both physical and social pain [49,50]. Thus, while previous studies connected synchrony
689 with pain alleviation through social bonding, the present study refines this claim by highlighting
690 a critical role for self-esteem. Consequently, a mere sense of social connection is not enough
691 to alleviate pain sensations, but meaningful and valuable social contributions appear more
692 crucial to foster a sense of belongingness that is often impaired in pathological conditions
693 [93,94].

694

695 **CONCLUSION**

696

697 This study demonstrates that (i) synchrony does not consistently reduce pain
698 sensations, (ii) that pain does not disrupt group synchrony, despite its physiological and
699 affective effects, that (iii) fear of pain induces stronger physiological responses than pain itself,
700 and finally (iv) the feeling of being "worthwhile" and effective in goal achievement may be key
701 in explaining pain alleviation rather than social bonding alone.

702

703 By nuancing previous findings, this study highlights the distinctive roles of emotional
704 arousal and valence in linking synchrony with pain, suggesting that pain can also act as a
705 social glue. Finally, these findings emphasize the potential role of "worthwhileness" as

706 described by the sociometer hypothesis. These insights pave the way for rehabilitation
707 interventions for pain conditions, which could leverage group synchronization to enhance
708 social belongingness and restore individual self-esteem.

709

710 REFERENCES

711

712 [1] Pikovsky, A., Rosenblum, M., & Kurths, J. (2002). Synchronization: a universal concept in
713 nonlinear science.

714 [2] Strogatz, S. H., & Stewart, I. (1993). Coupled oscillators and biological synchronization.
715 *Scientific american*, 269(6), 102-109.

716 [3] Tarr, B., Launay, J., & Dunbar, R. I. (2016). Silent disco: dancing in synchrony leads to
717 elevated pain thresholds and social closeness. *Evolution and Human Behavior*, 37(5), 343-
718 349.

719 [4] Schmidt, R. C., Fitzpatrick, P., Caron, R., & Mergeche, J. (2011). Understanding social
720 motor coordination. *Human movement science*, 30(5), 834-845.

721 [5] Varlet, M., Stoffregen, T. A., Chen, F. C., Alcantara, C., Marin, L., & Bardy, B. G. (2014).
722 Just the sight of you: postural effects of interpersonal visual contact at sea. *Journal of*
723 *Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 40(6), 2310.

724 [6] Mogan, R., Fischer, R., & Bulbulia, J. A. (2017). To be in synchrony or not? A meta-analysis
725 of synchrony's effects on behavior, perception, cognition and affect. *Journal of Experimental*
726 *Social Psychology*, 72, 13-20.

727 [7] Rennung, M., & Göritz, A. S. (2016). Prosocial consequences of interpersonal synchrony.
728 *Zeitschrift für Psychologie*.

729 [8] Hu, Y., Cheng, X., Pan, Y., & Hu, Y. (2022). The intrapersonal and interpersonal
730 consequences of interpersonal synchrony. *Acta Psychologica*, 224, 103513.

731 [9] Durkheim, É. (1912). *Les formes élémentaires de la vie religieuse. Le système totémique*
732 *en Australie. Livre I: Questions préliminaires*.

733 [10] Fawcett, C., & Tunçgenç, B. (2017). Infants' use of movement synchrony to infer social
734 affiliation in others. *Journal of experimental child psychology*, 160, 127-136.

735 [11] Bieńkiewicz, M. M., Smykovskiy, A. P., Olugbade, T., Janaqi, S., Camurri, A., Bianchi-
736 Berthouze, N., ... & Bardy, B. G. (2021). Bridging the gap between emotion and joint action.
737 *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 131, 806-833.

738 [12] Oullier, O., Kirman, A. P., & Kelso, J. S. (2008). The coordination dynamics of economic
739 decision making: a multilevel approach to social neuroeconomics. *IEEE Transactions on*
740 *Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, 16(6), 557-571.

741 [13] Reddish, P., Bulbulia, J., & Fischer, R. (2014). Does synchrony promote generalized
742 prosociality?. *Religion, Brain & Behavior*, 4(1), 3-19.

- 743 [14] Coutinho, J., Pereira, A., Oliveira-Silva, P., Meier, D., Lourenço, V., & Tschacher, W.
744 (2021). When our hearts beat together: Cardiac synchrony as an entry point to understand
745 dyadic co-regulation in couples. *Psychophysiology*, 58(3), e13739.
- 746 [15] Konvalinka, I., Xygalatas, D., Bulbulia, J., Schjødt, U., Jegindø, E. M., Wallot, S., ... &
747 Roepstorff, A. (2011). Synchronized arousal between performers and related spectators in a
748 fire-walking ritual. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(20), 8514-8519.
- 749 [16] Dumas, G., Lachat, F., Martinerie, J., Nadel, J., & George, N. (2011). From social
750 behaviour to brain synchronization: review and perspectives in hyperscanning. *Irbm*, 32(1),
751 48-53.
- 752 [17] Babiloni, F., & Astolfi, L. (2014). Social neuroscience and hyperscanning techniques: past,
753 present and future. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 44, 76-93.
- 754 [18] Goldstein, P., Weissman-Fogel, I., Dumas, G., & Shamay-Tsoory, S. G. (2018). Brain-to-
755 brain coupling during handholding is associated with pain reduction. *Proceedings of the*
756 *national academy of sciences*, 115(11), E2528-E2537.
- 757 [19] Zhao, Q., Zhao, W., Lu, C., Du, H., & Chi, P. (2024). Interpersonal neural synchronization
758 during social interactions in close relationships: A systematic review and meta-analysis of
759 fNIRS hyperscanning studies. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 105565.
- 760 [20] Feldman, R. (2007). Parent–infant synchrony and the construction of shared timing;
761 physiological precursors, developmental outcomes, and risk conditions. *Journal of Child*
762 *psychology and Psychiatry*, 48(3-4), 329-354.
- 763 [21] De Felice, S., Chand, T., Croy, I., Engert, V., Goldstein, P., Holroyd, C. B., ... & Vrticka,
764 P. (2024). Relational neuroscience: Insights from hyperscanning research. *Neuroscience &*
765 *Biobehavioral Reviews*, 105979.
- 766 [22] Hoehl, S., Fairhurst, M., & Schirmer, A. (2021). Interactional synchrony: signals,
767 mechanisms and benefits. *Social cognitive and affective neuroscience*, 16(1-2), 5-18.
- 768 [23] Koban, L., Ramamoorthy, A., & Konvalinka, I. (2019). Why do we fall into sync with
769 others? Interpersonal synchronization and the brain's optimization principle. *Social*
770 *Neuroscience*, 14(1), 1-9.
- 771 [24] Miles, L. K., Nind, L. K., Henderson, Z., & Macrae, C. N. (2010). Moving memories:
772 Behavioral synchrony and memory for self and others. *Journal of Experimental Social*
773 *Psychology*, 46(2), 457-460.
- 774 [25] Cross, L., Turgeon, M., & Atherton, G. (2019). How moving together binds us together:
775 the social consequences of interpersonal entrainment and group processes. *Open*
776 *Psychology*, 1(1), 273-302.
- 777 [26] Hove, M. J. and Risen, J. L. (2009). It's all in the timing: Interpersonal synchrony increases
778 affiliation. *Social cognition*, 27(6):949–960.

779 [27] Cross, L., Michael, J., Wilsdon, L., Henson, A., & Atherton, G. (2020). Still want to help?
780 Interpersonal coordination's effects on helping behaviour after a 24 hour delay. *Acta*
781 *Psychologica*, 206, 103062.

782 [28] Himberg, T., Laroche, J., Bigé, R., Buchkowski, M., & Bachrach, A. (2018). Coordinated
783 interpersonal behaviour in collective dance improvisation: the aesthetics of kinaesthetic
784 togetherness. *Behavioral Sciences*, 8(2), 23.

785 [29] Tschacher, W., Rees, G. M., & Ramseyer, F. (2014). Nonverbal synchrony and affect in
786 dyadic interactions. *Frontiers in psychology*, 5, 1323.

787 [30] Galbusera, L., Finn, M. T., Tschacher, W., & Kyselo, M. (2019). Interpersonal synchrony
788 feels good but impedes self-regulation of affect. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), 14691.

789 [31] Smykovskiy, A., Bieńkiewicz, M. M., Pla, S., Janaqi, S., & Bardy, B. G. (2022). Positive
790 emotions foster spontaneous synchronisation in a group movement improvisation task.
791 *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 16, 944241.

792 [32] Michael, J., Sebanz, N., and Knoblich, G. (2016). Observing joint action: Coordination
793 creates commitment. *Cognition*, 157:106–113.

794 [33] Tomasello, M., Melis, A. P., Tennie, C., Wyman, E., & Herrmann, E. (2012). Two key
795 steps in the evolution of human cooperation: The interdependence hypothesis. *Current*
796 *anthropology*, 53(6), 673-692.

797 [34] Fernández Castro, V., & Pacherie, E. (2021). Joint actions, commitments and the need to
798 belong. *Synthese*, 198(8), 7597-7626.

799 [35] Lang, M., Bahna, V., Shaver, J. H., Reddish, P., & Xygalatas, D. (2017). Sync to link:
800 Endorphin-mediated synchrony effects on cooperation. *Biological Psychology*, 127, 191-197.

801 [36] Cohen, E. E., Ejsmond-Frey, R., Knight, N., & Dunbar, R. I. (2010). Rowers' high:
802 behavioural synchrony is correlated with elevated pain thresholds. *Biology letters*, 6(1), 106-
803 108.

804 [37] Lewis, Z., & Sullivan, P. J. (2018). The effect of group size and synchrony on pain
805 threshold changes. *Small Group Research*, 49(6), 723-738.

806 [38] Sullivan, P., & Blacker, M. (2017). The effect of different phases of synchrony on pain
807 threshold in a drumming task. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 1034.

808 [39] Sullivan, P., Gagnon, M., Gammage, K., & Peters, S. (2015). Is the effect of behavioral
809 synchrony on cooperative behavior mediated by pain threshold?. *The Journal of social*
810 *psychology*, 155(6), 650-660.

811 [40] Sullivan, P. J., Rickers, K., & Gammage, K. L. (2014). The effect of different phases of
812 synchrony on pain threshold. *Group Dynamics: Theory, Research, and Practice*, 18(2), 122.

813 [41] Tarr, B., Launay, J., Cohen, E., & Dunbar, R. (2015). Synchrony and exertion during dance
814 independently raise pain threshold and encourage social bonding. *Biology letters*, 11(10),
815 20150767.

816 [42] Gilam, G., Gross, J. J., Wager, T. D., Keefe, F. J., & Mackey, S. C. (2020). What is the
817 relationship between pain and emotion? Bridging constructs and communities. *Neuron*,
818 107(1), 17-21.

819 [43] Eisenberger, N. I., & Lieberman, M. D. (2004). Why rejection hurts: a common neural
820 alarm system for physical and social pain. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 8(7), 294-300.

821 [44] MacDonald, G., & Leary, M. R. (2005). Why does social exclusion hurt? The relationship
822 between social and physical pain. *Psychological bulletin*, 131(2), 202.

823 [45] Machin, A. J., & Dunbar, R. I. (2011). The brain opioid theory of social attachment: a
824 review of the evidence. *Behaviour*, 148(9-10), 985-1025.

825 [46] Nummenmaa, L., Manninen, S., Tuominen, L., Hirvonen, J., Kalliokoski, K. K., Nuutila, P.,
826 ... & Sams, M. (2015). Adult attachment style is associated with cerebral μ -opioid receptor
827 availability in humans. *Human brain mapping*, 36(9), 3621-3628.

828 [47] Cacioppo, J. T., Cacioppo, S., Capitanio, J. P., & Cole, S. W. (2015). The
829 neuroendocrinology of social isolation. *Annual review of psychology*, 66(1), 733-767.

830 [48] Leary, M. R., Tambor, E. S., Terdal, S. K., & Downs, D. L. (1995). Self-esteem as an
831 interpersonal monitor: The sociometer hypothesis. *Journal of personality and social*
832 *psychology*, 68(3), 518.

833 [49] Tchalova, K., Beland, S., Chanda, M. L., Levitin, D. J., & Bartz, J. A. (2023). Shifting the
834 sociometer: opioid receptor blockade lowers self-esteem. *Social Cognitive and Affective*
835 *Neuroscience*, 18(1), nsad017.

836 [50] Onoda, K., Okamoto, Y., Nakashima, K. I., Nittono, H., Yoshimura, S., Yamawaki, S., ...
837 & Ura, M. (2010). Does low self-esteem enhance social pain? The relationship between trait
838 self-esteem and anterior cingulate cortex activation induced by ostracism. *Social cognitive and*
839 *affective neuroscience*, 5(4), 385-391.

840 [51] Gerber, J. P., Chang, S. H., & Reimel, H. (2017). Construct validity of Williams' ostracism
841 needs threat scale. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 115, 50-53.

842 [52] de Vignemont, F. (2024). La douleur: entre évaluation et action. *Revue de métaphysique*
843 *et de morale*, 121(1), 85-101.

844 [53] Craig, A. D. (2009). How do you feel—now? The anterior insula and human
845 awareness. *Nature reviews neuroscience*, 10(1), 59-70.

846 [54] Keefe, F. J., Lumley, M., Anderson, T., Lynch, T., & Carson, K. L. (2001). Pain and
847 emotion: new research directions. *Journal of clinical psychology*, 57(4), 587-607.

848 [55] Lumley, M. A., Cohen, J. L., Borszcz, G. S., Cano, A., Radcliffe, A. M., Porter, L. S., ... &
849 Keefe, F. J. (2011). Pain and emotion: a biopsychosocial review of recent research. *Journal*
850 *of clinical psychology*, 67(9), 942-968.

851 [56] de Vignemont, F. (2023). Expecting pain. *Synthese*, 202(5), 156.

852 [57] Miles, L. K., Griffiths, J. L., Richardson, M. J., & Macrae, C. N. (2010). Too late to
853 coordinate: Contextual influences on behavioral synchrony. *European Journal of Social*
854 *Psychology*, 40(1), 52-60.

855 [58] Smykovskiy, A., Janaqi, S., Pla, S., Jean, P., Bieńkiewicz, M., & Bardy, B. G. (2024).
856 Negative emotions disrupt intentional synchronization during group sensorimotor interaction.
857 *Emotion*, 24(3), 687.

858 [59] Paxton, A., & Dale, R. (2013). Argument disrupts interpersonal synchrony. *The Quarterly*
859 *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 66(11), 2092-2102.

860 [60] Kay, B. A., Kelso, J. A., Saltzman, E. L., & Schöner, G. (1987). Space-time behavior of
861 single and bimanual rhythmical movements: Data and limit cycle model. *Journal of*
862 *Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 13(2), 178.

863 [61] Schmitz, A., & Grillon, C. (2012). Assessing fear and anxiety in humans using the threat
864 of predictable and unpredictable aversive events (the NPU-threat test). *Nature protocols*, 7(3),
865 527-532.

866 [62] Haaker, J., Golkar, A., Selbing, I., & Olsson, A. (2017). Assessment of social transmission
867 of threats in humans using observational fear conditioning. *Nature Protocols*, 12(7), 1378-
868 1386.

869 [63] Lonsdorf, T. B., Menz, M. M., Andreatta, M., Fullana, M. A., Golkar, A., Haaker, J., ... &
870 Merz, C. J. (2017). Don't fear 'fear conditioning': Methodological considerations for the design
871 and analysis of studies on human fear acquisition, extinction, and return of fear. *Neuroscience*
872 *& Biobehavioral Reviews*, 77, 247-285.

873 [64] Bradley, M. M., & Lang, P. J. (1994). Measuring emotion: the self-assessment manikin
874 and the semantic differential. *Journal of behavior therapy and experimental psychiatry*, 25(1),
875 49-59.

876 [65] Grice-Jackson, T., Critchley, H. D., Banissy, M. J., & Ward, J. (2017). Common and
877 distinct neural mechanisms associated with the conscious experience of vicarious pain.
878 *Cortex*, 94, 152-163.

879 [66] Aron, A., Aron, E. N., & Smollan, D. (1992). Inclusion of other in the self scale and the
880 structure of interpersonal closeness. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 63(4), 596.

881 [67] Calabrese, C., Lombardi, M., Bollt, E., De Lellis, P., Bardy, B. G., & Di Bernardo, M.
882 (2021). Spontaneous emergence of leadership patterns drives synchronization in complex
883 human networks. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 18379.

884 [68] Virtanen, P., Gommers, R., Oliphant, T. E., Haberland, M., Reddy, T., Cournapeau, D., ...
885 & Van Mulbregt, P. (2020). SciPy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in
886 Python. *Nature methods*, 17(3), 261-272.

887 [69] Kuramoto, Y. (1975). Self-entrainment of a population of coupled non-linear oscillators. In
888 *International Symposium on Mathematical Problems in Theoretical Physics: January 23–29,*
889 *1975, Kyoto University, Kyoto/Japan* (pp. 420-422). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

890 [70] Karos, K., Meulders, A., Gatzounis, R., Seelen, H. A., Geers, R. P., & Vlaeyen, J. W.
891 (2017). Fear of pain changes movement: Motor behaviour following the acquisition of pain-
892 related fear. *European journal of pain*, 21(8), 1432-1442.

893 [71] Bohic, M., Pattison, L. A., Jhumka, Z. A., Rossi, H., Thackray, J. K., Ricci, M., ... & Abaira,
894 V. E. (2023). Mapping the neuroethological signatures of pain, analgesia, and recovery in
895 mice. *Neuron*, 111(18), 2811-2830.

896 [72] Makowski, D., Pham, T., Lau, Z. J., Brammer, J. C., Lespinasse, F., Pham, H., ... & Chen,
897 S. A. (2021). NeuroKit2: A Python toolbox for neurophysiological signal processing. *Behavior*
898 *research methods*, 1-8.

899 [73] Andersen, M. M., Schjoedt, U., Price, H., Rosas, F. E., Scrivner, C., & Clasen, M. (2020).
900 Playing with fear: A field study in recreational horror. *Psychological science*, 31(12), 1497-
901 1510.

902 [74] Bantinaki, K. (2012). The paradox of horror: Fear as a positive emotion. *The Journal of*
903 *Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, 70(4), 383-392.

904 [75] Karos, K., Meulders, A., Gatzounis, R., Seelen, H. A., Geers, R. P., & Vlaeyen, J. W.
905 (2017). Fear of pain changes movement: Motor behaviour following the acquisition of pain-
906 related fear. *European journal of pain*, 21(8), 1432-1442.

907 [76] Kroska, E. B. (2016). A meta-analysis of fear-avoidance and pain intensity: The paradox
908 of chronic pain. *Scandinavian journal of pain*, 13(1), 43-58.

909 [77] Asmundson, G. J., & Taylor, S. (1996). Role of anxiety sensitivity in pain-related fear and
910 avoidance. *Journal of behavioral medicine*, 19, 577-586.

911 [78] Fischer, R., & Kruekaew, J. (2020). Synchrony vs. pain in males and females: an
912 examination of differential effects on social bonding in a naturally occurring ritual. *Religion,*
913 *brain & behavior*, 10(4), 407-427.

914 [79] Peng, W., Lou, W., Huang, X., Ye, Q., Tong, R. K. Y., & Cui, F. (2021). Suffer together,
915 bond together: brain-to-brain synchronization and mutual affective empathy when sharing
916 painful experiences. *NeuroImage*, 238, 118249.

917 [80] Xygalatas, D., Mitkidis, P., Fischer, R., Reddish, P., Skewes, J., Geertz, A. W., ... &
918 Bulbulia, J. (2013). Extreme rituals promote prosociality. *Psychological science*, 24(8), 1602-
919 1605.

920 [81] Bastian, B., Jetten, J., & Ferris, L. J. (2014). Pain as social glue: Shared pain increases
921 cooperation. *Psychological science*, 25(11), 2079-2085.

922 [82] Salmela, M. (2014). Collective emotions as 'the glue' of group solidarity. *Solidarity: Theory*
923 *and practice*, 55.

924 [83] Shreesha, L., & Levin, M. (2024). Stress sharing as cognitive glue for collective
925 intelligences: A computational model of stress as a coordinator for morphogenesis.
926 *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 731, 150396.

927 [84] de Vignemont, F. (2024). Fear beyond danger. *Mind & Language*, 39(5), 647-663.

928 [85] Seligman, M. E. (1972). Learned helplessness. *Annual review of medicine*, 23(1), 407-
929 412.

930 [86] Botan, V., Bowling, N. C., Banissy, M. J., Critchley, H., & Ward, J. (2018). Individual
931 differences in vicarious pain perception linked to heightened socially elicited emotional states.
932 *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 2355.

933 [87] Botan, V., Fan, S., Critchley, H., & Ward, J. (2018). Atypical susceptibility to the rubber
934 hand illusion linked to sensory-localised vicarious pain perception. *Consciousness and*
935 *Cognition*, 60, 62-71.

936 [88] Bowling, N. C., Botan, V., Santiesteban, I., Ward, J., & Banissy, M. J. (2019). Atypical
937 bodily self-awareness in vicarious pain responders. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal*
938 *Society B*, 374(1787), 20180361.

939 [89] Hyde, J., Ryan, K. M., & Waters, A. M. (2019). Psychophysiological markers of fear and
940 anxiety. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, 21, 1-10.

941 [90] Chalaye, P., Devoize, L., Lafrenaye, S., Dallel, R., & Marchand, S. (2013). Cardiovascular
942 influences on conditioned pain modulation. *PAIN®*, 154(8), 1377-1382.

943 [91] Yi, W., Palmer, C., Serian, A., & Roy, M. (2025). Individualizing musical tempo to
944 spontaneous rates maximizes music-induced hypoalgesia. *Pain*,
945 10.1097/j.pain.0000000000003513.

946 [92] Flasbeck, V., Ramseyer, F. T., Schedlowski, M., Engler, H., & Brüne, M. (2024). Sick and
947 detached: Does experimental inflammation impact on movement synchrony in humans?.
948 *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity*.

949 [93] Baumeister, R. F., & Leary, M. R. (2017). The need to belong: Desire for interpersonal
950 attachments as a fundamental human motivation. *Interpersonal development*, 57-89.

951 [94] Michael, J., & Park, S. (2016). Anomalous bodily experiences and perceived social
952 isolation in schizophrenia: an extension of the social deafferentation
953 hypothesis. *Schizophrenia research*, 176(2-3), 392-397.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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Adapted items from Vicarious Pain Questionnaire

- 1. Avez-vous ressenti une sensation de douleur ?**
 - OUI
 - NON

- 2. À quel point cette expérience a été douloureuse pour vous ?**
 - NA/Pas de douleur
 - À peine ressentie
 - Légèrement ressentie
 - Ressentie
 - Assez désagréable/inconfortable*
 - Très désagréable/inconfortable

- 3. Comment décririez-vous cette expérience d'inconfort ?**
 - NA
 - Une sensation corporelle générale
 - Une sensation diffuse dans l'avant-bras
 - Une sensation localisée au niveau d'un point précis de l'avant-bras

- 4. Avez-vous ressenti un sentiment d'appréhension ?**
 - OUI
 - NON

- 5. Avez-vous ressenti un sentiment d'appréhension (peur) ?**
 - OUI
 - NON

- 6. Comment décririez-vous ce sentiment d'appréhension ?**
 - NA
 - Un sentiment peu présent
 - Un sentiment présent
 - Un sentiment très présent

***Intensity corresponding to the threshold measurement**

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Summary statistics for QUINTET experiment

	<i>STIMULATION</i>				<i>UNCERTAINT</i>
	<i>NO-VISION</i>	<i>VISION</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>	
Synchrony	0.44 ± 0.15	0.96 ± 0.05	0.95 ± 0.06	0.96 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.08
Frequency	0.46 ± 0.13	0.69 ± 0.12	0.81 ± 0.18	0.81 ± 0.18	0.95 ± 0.26
Amplitude	236.79 ± 38.91	235.56 ± 36.77	232.26 ± 35.07	231.80 ± 32.75	224.36 ± 33.90
Heart Rate	82.64 ± 10.34	83.57 ± 11.03	86.23 ± 12.37	86.95 ± 11.79	87.57 ± 11.77

1000 **Table A:** Mean and standard deviations from individual synchronization scores, movement
1001 frequency and amplitude scores across experimental conditions and trials with and without
1002 stimulation.

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	<i>NO-VISION</i>	<i>VISION</i>	<i>STIMULATION</i>	<i>UNCERTAINTY</i>
IOS	-0.37 ± 1.10	0.93 ± 1.11	1.33 ± 1.32	1.17 ± 1.63
VALENCE	-0.37 ± 1.27	-0.40 ± 1.61	-0.40 ± 1.63	-0.53 ± 1.55
AROUSAL	0.00 ± 1.70	0.50 ± 1.98	0.43 ± 2.25	-0.03 ± 2.24

1005 **Table B:** Mean and standard deviations from IOS, emotional valence and arousal scores
1006 across experimental conditions³.

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³ Scores are reported after baseline measures were removed.

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Summary statistics for QUARTET experiment

	<i>SOLO</i>	<i>TOGETHER</i>	<i>SYNCHRO</i>
<i>Individual contributions to synchrony</i>			
Baseline	.46 ± .10	.53 ± .19	.87 ± .18
Fear	.46 ± .09	.53 ± .20	.89 ± .17
Pain	.47 ± .09	.54 ± .20	.88 ± 0.18
<i>Movement Frequency</i>			
Baseline	0.60 ± 0.34	0.57 ± 0.17	0.67 ± 0.25
Fear	0.61 ± 0.37	0.57 ± 0.15	0.72 ± 0.24
Pain	0.58 ± 0.34	0.55 ± 0.20	0.72 ± 0.24
<i>Movement Amplitude</i>			
Baseline	245.58 ± 37.99	246.34 ± 31.35	235.01 ± 35.24
Fear	246.69 ± 39.38	247.26 ± 36.06	238.87 ± 38.54
Pain	252.61 ± 37.89	244.22 ± 39.17	229.50 ± 33.51
<i>Heart rates</i>			
Baseline	82.85 ± 13.26	82.71 ± 13.45	83.12 ± 13.24
Fear	85.48 ± 13.91	86.45 ± 14.82	86.63 ± 14.44
Pain	84.33 ± 11.64	84.53 ± 11.51	84.23 ± 11.24

1019 **Table C:** Mean and standard deviations from individual contribution to synchrony, movement
1020 frequency, amplitude and heart rates, across experimental conditions and trials.

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	<i>SOLO</i>		<i>TOGETHER</i>		<i>SYNCHRO</i>	
	<i>NO-STIM</i>	<i>STIM</i>	<i>NO-STIM</i>	<i>STIM</i>	<i>NO-STIM</i>	<i>STIM</i>
IOS	-0.36 ± 0.90	-0.42 ± 1.40	0.22 ± 1.26	-0.06 ± 1.86	1.11 ± 1.58	0.50 ± 1.42
Arousal	-0.47 ± 1.40	-0.31 ± 1.56	-0.89 ± 1.41	0.11 ± 2.03	-0.17 ± 1.89	0.28 ± 1.87
Valence	-0.50 ± 0.88	-1.36 ± 1.71	-1.00 ± 1.28	-1.78 ± 2.02	-0.72 ± 0.96	-1.28 ± 1.96

1028 **Table D:** Mean and standard deviations of IOS, Emotional Arousal and Valence scores across
1029 experimental conditions and participants receiving or not the unpleasant stimulation⁴.

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⁴ Scores are reported after baseline measures were removed.

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Complementary analyses on velocity and acceleration profiles

Exploratory analyses were performed on velocity and acceleration profiles to detect a possible effect of the stimulation on velocity and acceleration profiles. Visual inspection suggested indeed differences between trials with and without stimulation for some participants receiving the aversive electrodermal stimulation - see **Figure A** for graphical illustration.

The Earth Mover's distance (EMD), also known as the Wasserstein distance, was computed to provide an index of the amount of difference between two distributions. This method has been previously used to identify intra- and inter-individual differences in velocity profiles (Lozano-Goupil et al., 2021⁵; Słowiński et al., 2016⁶). However, applied to velocity and acceleration profiles and contrasting stimulated versus unstimulated trials, this measure failed to detect significant differences between time-series distributions in quintet experiment (all ps > .050).

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Figure A: Graphical illustration of acceleration time series (top) and their distributions (bottom) from a stimulated participant, with trials without stimulations represented in blue, trials with stimulation represented in red and stimulation represented with dark triangles.

⁵ Lozano-Goupil, J., Bardy, B. G., & Marin, L. (2021). Toward an emotional individual motor signature. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 647704.

⁶ Słowiński, P., Zhai, C., Alderisio, F., Salesse, R., Gueugnon, M., Marin, L., ... & Tsaneva-Atanasova, K. (2016). Dynamic similarity promotes interpersonal coordination in joint action. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 13(116), 20151093.

1075 Similar analyses were performed for the quartet experiment that revealed significant
1076 differences between baseline trials and trials with fear of a stimulation ($F(2, 148) = 3.63, p =$
1077 $.029, R^2 = .14$), with a trend for greater difference in the SOLO compared to the SYNCHRO
1078 condition (adjusted $p = .067$). A similar trend was observed when contrasting baseline trials
1079 and trials with stimulations ($F(2, 68) = 3.17, p = .048, R^2 = .19$), with a trend for greater
1080 differences in the SOLO compared to the SYNCHRO condition (adjusted $p = .064$). For
1081 acceleration, there was also significant differences between baseline trials and trials with
1082 stimulations ($F(2, 68) = 2.89, p = .062, R^2 = .11$). Considering the possible confounding effect
1083 of time, complementary analyses were performed using the order of experimental blocs as
1084 predictors. These analyses revealed a consistent decrease of the differences between velocity
1085 and acceleration profiles with time when contrasting baseline trials and trials with stimulations
1086 ($F(1, 69) = 7.89, p = .006, R^2 = .21$ and $F(1, 69) = 7.57, p = .008, R^2 = .13$ for velocity and
1087 acceleration respectively) and baseline trials with trials inducing a fear of stimulation ($F(1,$
1088 $149) = 20.42, p < .001, R^2 = .21$ and $F(1, 149) = 10.33, p = .002, R^2 = .14$ for velocity and
1089 acceleration respectively) - see **Figure B** for graphical illustration.
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1091 **Figure B:** Graphical illustration of acceleration time series (top) and their distributions (bottom)
1092 from a stimulated participant, with trials without stimulations represented in blue, trials with
1093 fear of stimulation in purple and trials with stimulations represented in red.
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